

Received: 16 August 2021/ Accepted: 21 August 2021/ Published: 31 August 2021
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5374372>

Green polymer nanocomposites

Prakash Chander Thapliyal*

Advanced Structural Composites and Durability Group, CSIR-Central Building Research Institute, Roorkee-247667, Uttarakhand, India.

*Correspondence: Prakash Chander Thapliyal (pcthapliyal@cbri.res.in, pct866@yahoo.com)

This work was presented at the International Online Conference on Nano Materials (ICN 2021) held during 9 – 11, April 2021 at Mahatma Gandhi University, Kerala, India, 686560

Introduction: Green materials are considered as next-gen contenders for lightweight and sustainable nanocomposites. Several natural and synthetic green polymers and eco-friendly nanofillers have been employed to form sustainable green materials. In particular green polymer nanocomposites demonstrate distinctive properties of adding together the advantages of natural fillers and organic polymers. Plant fibers are found apt to reinforce polymers as they have rather high strength, low price of acquisition and create low carbon dioxide discharge. They are also biodegradable and are renewable compared to other fibrous materials. Organic polymers on the other hand, are desirable for the reason that they are either recyclable or biodegradable with no environmental hazards. Lately, awareness has arisen to the use of bio-reinforced composites in construction, packaging and therapeutic applications due to increased apprehension for environmental sustainability. This work will review some of the contemporary research efforts, trends, challenges and state of affairs in the field of green polymer nanocomposites.

Methods: In a typical procedure, leaves and stem of plants were collected, dried out and pulverized. Water extractive (both hot and cold) added to polymeric resin in different ratios. All these coating compositions were stabilized using synthesized nanofiller and other procured additives. Nanocomposite coatings were then characterized for their properties as per relevant standard procedures.

Results & Discussions: During the physic-mechanical investigations, developed green polymer nanocomposite coatings have shown good elongation, low water vapour transmission and excellent bond strength. Hence it can be concluded that these developed nanocomposite coatings are better than conventional ones if renewable content aspect is considered and definitely will have less significant carbon footprints.

Conclusions: Initial results are supporting the methodology employed. However more studies are the need of the hour to know effects of plant extracts on properties of green nanocomposite coatings and their suitability towards better sustainability.

Keywords: *Nanocomposites, Polymers, Plant fibers, Green, Sustainable*

Acknowledgment: *Author wish to acknowledge the support and encouragement provided by Director, CSIR-Central Building Research Institute, Roorkee for carrying out this work.*

References

1. Thapliyal PC. Protective Coatings having Renewable Content Contributing towards Sustainability in Buildings. Macromol Symposia. 2021, In Print.
2. IS 101, Bureau of Indian Standards, 2017.